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Correlates Of Students' Academic Performance In Kwara South Senatorial District, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated teachers' application of classroom management skills as correlates of students' academic performance in Kwara South Senatorial District, Nigeria. Two research questions guided the study, while two hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population was 826 teachers from 98 public secondary schools in Kwara South Senatorial District, Nigeria with a sample of 248 respondents. The instrument used for data collection was two sets of questionnaires titled "Teachers' Application of Classroom Management Skills Questionnaire (TACMSQ) and Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire (SAPQ)". The instrument was validated by three experts, two in Educational Management in the Department of Educational Foundations and one in Department of Science and Mathematics Education, all in Faculty of Education Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi. The researcher administered the instruments to 30 respondents in one public secondary school in Kwara South Senatorial District, Nigeria. The reliability test was conducted using Cronbach Alpha reliability. The result yielded reliability coefficients of 0.90 for TPDPQ and 0.93 for TJSQ. Data were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) to answer the five research questions and test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study showed that teachers' application of classroom management skills such as classroom organization skill and students' engagement skill has a very strong significant positive relationship with students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Kwara South Senatorial District, Nigeria. It was recommended that teachers in public secondary schools should adopt effective classroom organization techniques such as clear lesson planning, structured seating arrangements and efficient time management to maintain order and focus during lessons. Also, administrators of public secondary schools should provide strong instructional leadership by ensuring that teachers employ strategies that actively engage students during lessons.

Keywords: teachers' application of classroom management skills, classroom organization skill, students' engagement skill and students' academic performance.

INTRODUCTION

The challenge of students' academic performance remains a critical global concern that attracts attention of government, educational administrators, teachers and parents. This challenge may be influenced by multifaceted factors including socio-economic status, school infrastructure, teacher quality and educational policies. At global level, disparities persist between and within countries with developing nations like Nigeria, Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Indonesia and Bangladesh facing pronounced challenges such as inadequate funding, overcrowded classrooms and limited access to quality teaching resources (United Nations Education Scientific and Cultural Organization, 2023).

In Nigeria, the problem of students' academic performance may be compounded by systemic issues such as frequent industrial actions by educators, poor curriculum implementation and regional disparities in education quality. Specifically, in Kwara South Senatorial District, students seem to face unique difficulties such as rural-urban educational gaps, insufficient educational facilities, limited teacher motivation and application of classroom management skills, all of which undermine consistent academic performance (Adeyemi & Olayemi, 2022). These barriers reflect the broader global struggle to ensure equitable and quality education for all, as emphasized by Sustainable Development Goal 4 which aims at ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education and promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all (United Nations, 2023).

Students' academic performance refers to the measurable outcomes of learners' engagement and achievement in educational activities, often evaluated through assessments, examinations, and continuous evaluation methods within formal school settings (Obiunu, 2015). It reflects how well students meet educational objectives and curriculum standards, influenced by factors such as teaching quality, school infrastructure, socio-economic background, and parental involvement (Ayooseh & Iorkyosu, 2018). Students' academic performance in Nigeria appears to be declining overtime. Ajibade and Ajibade (2020) highlight the poor academic performance, noting that about 93% of secondary school graduates each year fail to meet the qualifications for university education due to their subpar academic results. Ajibade and Ajibade (2020) observe that this is evident in the West African Senior Secondary Certificate Examinations (WASSCE) between 2015 and 2020 in which many students failed to secure at least five credits, including English Language and Mathematics in their examinations.

In public secondary schools in Kwara South Senatorial District, Nigeria, the perceived poor students' academic performance appears to remain a worrying trend which could be as a result of many reasons including teachers' ineffective application of classroom management skills. Emmer and Evertson (2016) identify classroom management skills such as setting clear expectations, communication, maintaining consistency and using positive reinforcement that could affect students' academic performance. Obiunu (2015) similarly highlights motivation, students' engagement, managing time efficiently, fostering student engagement, maintaining classroom discipline, classroom organization, building respectful relationships, monitoring student behaviour and adapting strategies to diverse needs. This study therefore focuses on teachers' classroom organization, students' engagement, maintenance of classroom discipline, communication and students' motivation. This is because these skills appear to have positively or negatively correlate with students' academic performance in the study area.

Teachers' classroom organization skill refers to the way educators arrange physical space, materials, time and routines to create an environment that supports effective teaching and learning (Adeosun, 2021). Effective classroom organization by teachers may affect students' academic performance in schools. This is because organized classrooms may foster a structured learning environment that enhance students' engagement, reduces disruptive behaviour and maximizes instructional time. When teachers manage classroom space, resources and time efficiently, students may be more likely to stay focused and achieve better academic outcomes. It has shown that clear routines, well-planned lessons and effective classroom management strategies contribute to improved student achievement (Yusuf & Adigun, 2020).

Teachers' application of classroom organization skill describes the orderly and professional arrangement and coordination of classroom activities in order to provide an environment conducive for teaching and learning (Kumar & Liu, 2019). Ahmad, Hussain, Alia, Mubarka and Batool (2017) opine that classroom organization procedures assume an indispensable part in upgrading learners' learning. Nwankwoala (2018) further describes classroom organization as all the effects the classroom teacher puts using the available human and material resources in the classroom to achieve set educational objectives and goals. Classroom organization involves the exercises to arrange and guide classes to accomplish particular objectives. To keep up a positive learning condition in the classroom is teachers' obligation. A very much organized classroom offers a helpful domain for compelling teaching and learning. In Nigerian where public secondary schools often face challenges such as overcrowded classrooms and limited resources,

strong organizational skills among teachers may become more critical for promoting positive academic outcomes supported by effective teachers' students' engagement.

Teachers' students' engagement skill is seen as the strategies by which teachers actively involve students in the learning process, fostering attention, curiosity and motivation (Adeyemi & Adu, 2023). This may relate with students' academic performance because when teachers actively engage students through interactive teaching methods, timely feedback and supportive classroom environments, students may develop interest in learning, demonstrate higher motivation and achieve better academic outcomes. Engaged teachers may foster positive student-teacher relationships, which are essential for improving students' cognitive and emotional involvement in their studies. Enhancing teacher-student engagement can therefore serve as a key strategy to improve academic performance (Yusuf & Dada, 2022).

Varying degrees of engagement are evident both within an individual student and across specific students. However, McInerney (2020) suggests that teachers play an important role in promoting positive relationships with students by understanding the students' background and building a learning environment that focuses on relevant and meaningful learning experiences to enhance student involvement in their learning process. Hershkovitz (2018) states that teachers need to understand student's attitudes and beliefs which affect their involvement and achievement in classroom. Hershkovitz further highlights Bandura's Social Learning Theory that emphasizes on three interrelated components in understanding student's engagement in classroom. The components are: individual component (self-esteem, trust and attitude), behaviour component (achievement or response to the situation) and environment component (peers feedback, parents and teachers). Similarly, Salleh, Desa and Tuit (2023) reinforce that self-esteem, academic performance and feedback from others may affect the involvement of students. It is based on the above background this study sought to investigate the relationship between teachers' application of classroom management skills and students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Kwara South Senatorial District, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The significance of teachers' application of classroom management skills lies in their ability to create an organized, conducive, and engaging learning environment that enhances students' academic achievement and positive behaviour. Students' academic performance in public secondary schools is a critical factor for determining their access to higher education opportunities, shaping future career prospects and contributing to the nation's overall socio-economic development. Despite the significance of students' academic performance, in Kwara South Senatorial District of Nigeria, concerns have been raised regarding the perceived low students' academic performance especially in public secondary schools. This concern may not be far from teacher factors including inconsistent application of classroom management skills such as classroom organization, student engagement, maintenance of discipline, communication and students' motivation. Studies have shown that poor classroom management often results in increased student disruptions, reduced instructional time and lowered academic outcomes (Adeniji, 2017; Emmer & Evertson, 2016). Despite government efforts to improve teaching effectiveness, many secondary school teachers in the district seem to struggle with implementing consistent and impactful classroom management skills that align with best practices.

The researcher observed that there is ineffective classroom organization by teachers. Teachers seem to be ineffective in actively engaging students, enforce classroom discipline, communicate effectively and foster motivation making student to perform better academically. The researcher also observed that limited localized research exists to clearly demonstrate the extent to which these classroom management variables influence students' academic performance in the study area. This gap necessitates a focused investigation into how teachers' application of classroom management skills can have relationship with students' academic performance in public secondary schools Kwara South Senatorial District, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate relationship between teachers' application of classroom management skills and students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Kwara South Senatorial District, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to find out:

1. relationship between teachers’ application of classroom organization skill and students’ academic performance in public secondary schools in Kwara South Senatorial District, Nigeria.
2. relationship between teachers’ application of students’ engagement skill and students’ academic performance in public secondary schools.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between teachers’ application of classroom organization skill and students’ academic performance in public secondary schools in Kwara South Senatorial District, Nigeria?
2. What is the relationship between teachers’ application of students’ engagement skill and students’ academic performance in public secondary schools?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Teachers’ application of classroom organization skill has no significant relationship with students’ academic performance in public secondary schools in Kwara South Senatorial District, Nigeria.
2. Teachers’ application of students’ engagement skill has no significant relationship with students’ academic performance in public secondary schools.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population was 826 teachers from 98 public secondary schools in Kwara South Senatorial District, Nigeria with a sample of 248 respondents. The instrument used for data collection was two sets of questionnaires titled "Teachers’ Application of Classroom Management Skills Questionnaire (TACMSQ) and Students’ Academic Performance Questionnaire (SAPQ)". The instrument was validated by three experts, two in Educational Management in the Department of Educational Foundations and one in Department of Science and Mathematics Education, all in Faculty of Education Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi. The researcher administered the instruments to 30 respondents in one public secondary school in Kwara South Senatorial District, Nigeria. The reliability test was conducted using Cronbach Alpha reliability. The result yielded reliability coefficients of 0.90 for TPDPQ and 0.93 for TJSQ. Data were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) to answer the five research questions and test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

A total of 248 copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents. However, 245 representing 99.1% copies of questionnaire were returned by the respondents while three representing 1% copies of questionnaire were recorded as attrition. The data obtained from the questionnaire were presented, analyzed and interpreted.

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between teachers’ application of classroom organization skill and students’ academic performance in public secondary schools in Kwara South Senatorial District, Nigeria?*

Table 1: Correlation between Teachers’ Application of Classroom Organization Skill and Students’ Academic Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Kwara South Senatorial District, Nigeria

Variables	N	r	Decision
Teachers’ Application of Classroom Organization Skill	245	0.88	Very Strong Positive Relationship
Students’ Academic Performance	245		

* Correlation coefficient is significant at $p < 0.05$

The result presented in table 1 indicates correlation coefficient (r) = 0.88. This result reveals a very strong positive relationship between teachers' application of classroom organization skill and students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Kwara South Senatorial District, Nigeria.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between teachers' application of students' engagement skill and students' academic performance in public secondary schools?

Table 2:

Correlation between Teachers' Application of Students' Engagement Skill and Students' Academic Performance in Public Secondary Schools

Variables	N	r	Decision
Teachers' Application of Students' Engagement Skill	245	0.93	Very Strong Positive Relationship
Students' Academic Performance	245		

* Correlation coefficient is significant at $p < 0.05$

The result presented in table 2 indicates correlation coefficient (r) = 0.93. This result reveals a very strong positive relationship between teachers' application of students' engagement skill and students' academic performance in public secondary schools.

Hypothesis 1: Teachers' application of classroom organization skill has no significant relationship with students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Kwara South Senatorial District, Nigeria.

Table 3: *Pearson Product Movement Correlation Test of Teachers' Application of Classroom Organization Skill and Students' Academic Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Kwara South Senatorial District, Nigeria*

Variables	N	r	P	Decision
Teachers' Application of Classroom Organization Skill	245	0.88	0.000	Very Strong Significant Positive Relationship
Students' Academic Performance	245			

* Correlation coefficient is significant at $p < 0.05$

The result in Table 3 shows that (r) = 0.88; $p < 0.05$. Since the calculated p-value (0.000) is less than the significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis which states that teachers' application of classroom organization skill has no significant relationship with students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Kwara South Senatorial District, Nigeria was rejected. This implies that teachers' application of classroom organization skill has very strong significant positive relationship with students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Kwara South Senatorial District, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2:

Teachers' application of students' engagement skill has no significant relationship with students' academic performance in public secondary schools.

Table 4: *Pearson Product Movement Correlation Test of Teachers' Application of Students' Engagement Skill and Students' Academic Performance in Public Secondary Schools*

Variables	N	r	P	Decision
Teachers' Application of Students' Engagement Skill	245	0.93	0.000	Very Strong Significant Positive Relationship
Students' Academic Performance	245			

* Correlation coefficient is significant at $p < 0.05$

The result in Table 4 shows that $(r) = 0.93$; $p < 0.05$. Since the calculated p-value (0.000) is less than the significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis which states that teachers' application of students' engagement skill has no significant relationship with students' academic performance in public secondary schools was rejected. This implies that teachers' application of students' engagement skill has very strong significant positive relationship with students' academic performance in public secondary schools.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This section presents discussion of findings as follows:

The first finding of the study revealed that teachers' application of classroom organization skills has a very strong significant positive relationship with students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Kwara South Senatorial District, Nigeria. This finding implies that when teachers effectively organize their classrooms, learning becomes more structured and conducive, enabling students to concentrate better and perform well academically. The finding is in line with the study of Ossai (2023) whose findings revealed that effective classroom organization by teachers positively relates to students' academic performance. It also agrees with the findings of Ezemba, Nnorom, Anyaeji, and Ezeanolue (2021), who reported that classroom organizational and management practices significantly and positively relate to students' academic performance. The researcher further observes that teachers' application of classroom organization skills enhances students' academic performance because a well-organized classroom minimizes distractions, fosters active learning, and promotes effective teacher-student interaction.

The second finding of the study revealed that teachers' application of students' engagement skills has a very strong significant positive relationship with students' academic performance in public secondary schools. This finding implies that when teachers actively engage students in learning activities, their interest, participation, and understanding of concepts improve, leading to better academic outcomes. The finding is consistent with the study of Nixon and Williams (2024), whose research revealed that students' engagement has a significant positive correlation with class participation and learning outcomes. It also aligns with the findings of Varga (2017), who showed that students' engagement has a significant relationship with academic performance in Maryland. Generally, teachers' application of students' engagement skills enhances academic performance because it promotes interaction, critical thinking, and sustained attention during lessons.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the study, it was concluded that teachers' application of classroom management skills such as classroom organization skill, students' engagement skill, classroom discipline skill, communication skill and students' motivation skill has a very strong significant positive relationship with students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Kwara South Senatorial District, Nigeria. This implies effective application of classroom management can bring about desirable outcome in students' academic performance in public secondary schools.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

4. Teachers in public secondary schools should adopt effective classroom organization techniques such as clear lesson planning, structured seating arrangements and efficient time management to maintain order and focus during lessons. This may go a long way in reducing distractions, maximizing learning time and ensuring that students are better able to concentrate, thereby leading to improved academic performance in public secondary schools.
5. Administrators of public secondary schools should provide strong instructional leadership by ensuring that teachers employ strategies that actively engage students during lessons. They should also encourage the use of interactive teaching methods such as group discussions, project-based learning, and the use of instructional materials that stimulate participation. This could help sustain students' interest, improve their understanding of concepts, and consequently enhance their academic performance.

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